

Designing and synthesis of macrocyclic Schiff base ligand : Study of interaction with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and biological screening

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The synthesis of a tetradentate ligand i.e. 3,4,12,13-tetraphenyl-2,5,11,14,19,20-hexaaza tricyclo[13.3.1.1⁶⁻¹⁰]cosa 1(19),2,4,6,8,10(20),11,13,15,17-decaene (L) and its complexes with manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) have been reported. The complexes are characterized by the elemental analysis, molar conductance measurements, magnetic susceptibility measurements, mass, ¹H NMR, IR, electronic, and EPR spectral studies. On the basis of molar conductance the complexes may be formulated as [M(L)X₂] [where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and X = Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻] due to non-electrolyte nature in dimethylformamide (DMF). All the complexes are of high spin type and found to be six-coordinated.

On the basis of IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies an octahedral geometry was proposed for Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes and tetragonal geometry for Cu^{II} complexes. The antimicrobial activities of the ligand and complexes have been screened *in vitro* against many bacteria and pathogenic fungi to study their growth inhibition capacity.

Synthetic macrocycles are a growing class of compounds with varying chemistry¹⁻⁵ viz. donating atoms, ring size and type of reaction. The chemical properties of macrocyclic complexes can be tuned to force metal ions to adopt unusual coordination geometry. Transition metal macrocyclic complexes have received much attention as an active part of metalloenzymes⁶ as biomimic model compounds^{7,8} due to its resemblance with natural proteins like hemerythrin and enzymes. The complexes of this type are also useful in catalysis⁹. These help us in further understanding the biological systems⁹. In view of the above discussion we report in the present paper, the comparative determination of structure, function, relationship underlying metal ion binding by the pyridine containing nitrogen donor[N₄] macrocyclic ligand L (Fig. 1), having the 20-membered backbone with the Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal ions.

Fig. 1. Preparation and the structure of the ligand (L).

Results and discussion

The formation of the ligand and the complexes may be represented by the following reactions :

On the basis of elemental analysis, the complexes were assigned to possess the composition shown in Table I. The molar conductance data of the complexes in DMF correspond to non-electrolyte nature¹⁰. These complexes may be formulated as [M(L)X₂] [M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and X = Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻]. The EI mass spectra of ligand (L) shows a final peak at 565u corresponding to the macrocyclic moiety [(C₃₈H₂₆N₆)⁺ atomic mass 565]. Other peaks like 11, 26, 77, 105, 152, 203, 263, 308u and 411u etc. corresponds to various fragments. In the ¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand, presence of a sharp multiplet in the region δ 7.28 may be assigned for the benzenoid hydrogen (26H)¹¹. IR spectrum of the ligand does not exhibit any band corresponding for the free primary diamine and hydroxyl group⁵ which suggest the complete condensation of amino group with keto group, the band present at 720–780 cm⁻¹ and 1430–1630 cm⁻¹ corresponding to phenyl group^{12,13}. The vibration due to ν(C=N) skeletal are present in the region 1405 cm⁻¹. The strong frequencies of ca. 1595

Table 1. Molar conductance, magnetic moment and electronic spectral data of the complexes

Complex	Colour	Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	Yield %	μ_{eff} B.M.	Electronic spectral data $\lambda_{\text{max}} (\text{cm}^{-1})$
$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6$ (ligand)	Cream	—	73	—	—
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	Greenish gray	12.63	69	5.94	17988, 24784, 28901, 31674
$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{26}\text{MnN}_6\text{Cl}_2$					
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	Light brown	16.42	74	6.02	18325, 25098, 29415, 32573
$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{26}\text{MnN}_8\text{O}_6$					
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	Shiny black	12.33	68	5.01	8966, 14458, 20401
$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{26}\text{CoN}_6\text{Cl}_2$					
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	Pink	11.65	79	4.97	8562, 14180, 21018
$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{26}\text{CoN}_8\text{O}_6$					
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	Dark brown	13.17	63	3.01	10256, 16636, 24674
$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{26}\text{NiN}_6\text{Cl}_2$					
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	Green	12.72	67	3.00	10675, 15778, 24635
$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{26}\text{NiN}_8\text{O}_6$					
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	Black	10.57	76	2.01	10701, 13209, 15595
$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{26}\text{CuN}_6\text{Cl}_2$					
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	Brown	11.69	73	1.99	10919, 12241, 16233
$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{26}\text{CuN}_8\text{O}_6$					

cm^{-1} are usually associated to $\nu(\text{CN})$ couple with phenyl ring vibrations. A band appearing at 1635 cm^{-1} may be assigned to symmetric or asymmetric $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ vibrations. The shifting of the $(\text{C}=\text{N})$ bands toward the lower side in the complexes indicates the coordination through the nitrogen atoms. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses. The higher melting point of the complexes than the metal free ligand suggests the thermal stability of the complexes.

IR spectra of the complexes : The presence of the absorption bands at $1407\text{--}1415$, $1301\text{--}1310$ and $1019\text{--}1025 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, in the IR spectra of the nitrate complexes suggest that both the nitrate groups are coordinated to the central metal ion in an unidentate arrangement¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

Manganese(II) complexes : The magnetic moment, at room temperature, lie in the range $5.94\text{--}6.02$ B.M. corresponding to five unpaired electrons. Electronic spectra of Mn^{II} complexes, display four weak intensity absorption bands (Table 1). These bands may be assigned to the transitions, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g} ({}^4G) (10B + 5C)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g ({}^4D) (17B + 5C)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4P) (7B + 7C)$, respectively^{17,18}.

The EPR spectra were recorded at room temperature as polycrystalline sample and in the solution of DMF. The polycrystalline sample give one broad isotropic signal centered at approximately, the free electron g -value (2.0023). Observed g -values are in the range $2.02\text{--}2.03$. The broad-

ening of spectra probably is due to spin relaxation¹⁷. In DMF solution the complexes give EPR spectra containing six lines arising due to hyperfine interaction between the unpaired electrons with the ${}^{55}\text{Mn}$ nucleus ($I = 5/2$). The nuclear magnetic quantum number, M_I , corresponding to the lines $-5/2, -3/2, -1/2, +1/2, +3/2, +5/2$ from low to high field.

Various ligand field parameters have been calculated and are given in Table 3.

Cobalt(II) complexes : At room temperature the magnetic moment measurements of the cobalt(II) complexes lie in the range $4.97\text{--}5.01$ B.M. corresponding to three unpaired electrons. The electronic spectral bands may be assigned to the transitions, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g} (\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$, respectively. EPR spectra of the Co^{II} complexes was recorded as polycrystalline sample and in DMF solution at liquid nitrogen temperature to avoid the broadened of the lines at higher temperature. The large deviation in g values, in the EPR spectra, from the spin only value ($g = 2.0023$) is due to the large angular momentum contribution.

The calculated ligand field parameters are listed in Table 3.

Nickel(II) complexes : The magnetic moment lies in the range $2.96\text{--}2.98$ B.M. These values are in tune with a high spin configuration and show the presence of an octahedral environment around the Ni^{II} ion in all the complexes reported in this paper¹⁶⁻¹⁹. Electronic bands are assigned to

Table 2. EPR spectral data of the complexes

Complex	Polycrystalline sample				In DMF solution				
	$g_{\parallel}$	$g_{\perp}$	g_{iso}	G	$g_{\parallel}$	$g_{\perp}$	g_{iso}/A	G	
[Mn(L)Cl ₂]	–	–	2.03	–	–	–	128.33	–	
[Mn(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	–	–	2.03	–	–	–	121.66	–	
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	2.37	2.13	2.21	2.85	2.33	2.12	2.19	2.75	
[Co(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	2.29	2.09	2.16	3.11	2.27	2.10	2.16	2.70	
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	2.14	2.06	2.09	2.33	2.19	2.05	2.10	3.80	
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	2.19	2.06	2.10	3.17	2.12	2.05	2.07	2.40	

Table 3. Ligand field parameters of the complexes

Complex	Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B (cm ⁻¹)	β	C (cm ⁻¹)	ν_2/ν_1	F_4	F_2	H_x	LFSE (kJ mol ⁻¹)
[Mn(L)Cl ₂]	1798.80	588.00	0.75	3780	1.38	108	1128	3.57	00
[Mn(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	1832.50	617.00	0.78	3785	1.37	108	1157	3.14	00
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	1049.68	1093.41	0.78	–	1.61	–	–	–	100.33
[Co(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	1002.38	1044.15	0.73	–	1.65	–	–	–	95.81
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	1025.60	702.80	0.67	2811	1.62	–	–	–	147.04
[Ni(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	1067.50	559.20	0.54	2237	1.47	–	–	–	153.05

the transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. The position of bands indicate that the complexes have an octahedral geometry and might possess D_{4h} symmetry¹⁸.

Copper(II) complexes : The value of magnetic moment 1.99–2.01 B.M. corresponds to one unpaired electron. The complexes may be considered to possess a tetragonal geometry.

The electronic spectral bands may be assigned to the transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$) ν_1 , ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$) ν_2 and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{zy}, d_{yz}$) ν_3 respectively^{20,21}. The EPR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes exhibit a well-resolved anisotropic signal in the parallel and perpendicular ⁶³Cu region^{22,23}. The observed data show that $g_{\parallel} = 2.12$ – 2.19 and $g_{\perp} = 2.05$ – 2.06 (Table 2). The values of $g_{\parallel}$ and $g_{\perp}$ are closer to 2 and $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$. This suggest major distortion in the copper(II) complexes from O_h symmetry to D_{4h} symmetry^{24,25}.

Electrochemical behaviour : The cyclic voltammograms of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes in 10^{-3} M TBAP-DMF solution were recorded at room temperature, using a glassy carbon as working electrode. The microelectrode radius was 5.0 μ m and the scan rate was 100 mV s⁻¹. The complexes exhibits two one electron quasi reversible peaks, corresponding to the Ni^{II} $\rightarrow$ Ni^{III}, Cu^{II} $\rightarrow$ Cu^{III} and Ni^{II} $\rightarrow$ Ni^I, Cu^{II} $\rightarrow$ Cu^I processes respectively. It was to compare the redox potential of the complexes.

On comparing the cyclic voltammograms we observe

that the variation in oxidation reduction potential is may be due to distortion in geometry that arises due to different metals in coordination but the difference in $E_{1/2}$ value between nickel and copper complexes is less.

Biological study :

The ligand (L) and its complexes were evaluated against different species of bacteria and fungi as per the procedure reported earlier^{26,27}.

Antibacterial screening : The compounds were screened against *Sarcina lutea* (gram positive), *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram positive) and *Escherchia coli* (gram negative) bacteria. The results of the antibacterial screening are given in Table 4.

Antifungal screening : *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus glaucus*, *Ustilago tritici* and *Ustilago scitamineae* fungi were used as the test organism for all the newly synthesized compounds. The results of the antifungal screening are given in Table 4.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade, and procured from Fluka. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received. All solvents used were purified according to standard procedures.

Synthesis of ligand : Hot ethanolic solution (20 ml each) of benzil (4.2046 g, 0.02 mol), and 2,6-diaminopyridine (2.1826 g, 0.02 mol) were mixed slowly with constant stir-

Table 4. Antimicrobial screening data of the complexes

Complex	Antibacterial results			Antifungal results			
	<i>Sarcina lutea</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. glaucus</i>	<i>U. tritici</i>	<i>U. scitamineae</i>
Ligand (L)	++	++	++	**	**	**	**
[Mn(L)Cl ₂]	+	++	+	*	*	**	*
[Mn(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	++	+	+	**	*	*	**
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	++	+++	++	****	***	****	****
[Co(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	++	++	+++	****	****	***	***
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	+++	+++	++	***	**	**	**
[Ni(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	++	++	++	**	**	**	***
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	++++	++++	+++	***	***	***	***
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	++++	+++	++++	***	**	***	***

ring. This mixture was refluxed at 85°C for 5 h in the presence of few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid. On cooling a solid cream-colored precipitate formed, which was filtered, washed with cold EtOH, and dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀. Yield 73%, m.p. 258°C (Found : C, 80.63; H, 4.53; N, 14.79. Calcd. for C₃₈H₂₆N₆: C, 80.54; H, 4.59; N, 14.84%).

Synthesis of complexes :

Hot ethanolic (20 ml each) solution of ligand (1.1320 g, 0.002 mol) and corresponding metal salts (0.001 mol) were mixed together with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 5–11 h at 70–92°C. On cooling, colored complex precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with cold EtOH and dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀.

Physical measurements : All the analysis was done on standard instruments²⁸.

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